

SHORT NOTES

Spectrophotometric Determination of the Thermodynamic Ionisation Constant of 3,5-Dinitrobenzoic Acid in Aqueous Solution

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Measurements of the extent of ionisation were previously made by the method of visual colorimetry by Hammett and co-workers¹ and also applied to spectrophotometry in the ultraviolet region for cases where there was no visible change in colour². The present investigation involves determination of the thermodynamic ionisation constant of 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid in aqueous solution on which no data exist in the literature.

A recrystallised B. D. H. sample of 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid was used for preparing solutions. The other chemicals used for preparing acid standard, base standard, and buffer solution were of AnalaR quality of B.D.H. A Hilger Uvispec spectrophotometer (Model H700.308 of Hilger & Watts Ltd., London) having 1 cm effective light path was used for studying the absorption spectra. Absorption of the acid was determined in (a) 0.1*M*-HCl; (b) a buffer containing Na acetate (1.25 ml of 0.1*M*) and acetic acid (23.75 ml of 0.1*M*); (c) 0.1*M*-NaOH. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

3,5-Dinitrobenzoic acid = $3.32M \times 10^{-3}$. Temp. = $30.3^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$.

Wave length.	Absorbances in			ρK_c .
	0.1 <i>M</i> -HCl.	Buffer (pH 3.05).	0.1 <i>M</i> -NaOH.	
440m μ	0.0223	0.0655	0.1249	2.19
430	0.0300	0.0900	0.1534	3.07
425	0.0350	0.1010	0.1630	3.02
420	0.0395	0.1107	0.1700	2.97
415	0.0438	0.1192	0.1739	2.91
410	0.0482	0.1249	0.1750	2.87
405	0.0580	0.1308	0.1772	2.85
400	0.0665	0.1379	0.1805	2.83
395	0.0809	0.1487	0.1858	2.79
390	0.1024	0.1643	0.1990	2.80
385	0.1319	0.1805	0.2218	2.98
380	0.1700	0.2218	0.2557	2.78
376	0.2218	0.2876	0.3054	2.96

Average 2.87 ± 0.1 1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 2721; 1934, 56, 827; *Chem. Rev.*, 1935, 16, 87.2. Hammett, *Chem. Rev.*, 1933, 13, 61; Flexner *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 2103,

The ionisation constant K_0 is given by

$$pK_0 = pH + \log \frac{b - e}{e - a} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where the pH is that of the buffer solution of the acid having absorbance 'e' and 'a' and 'b' are the absorbances of the same concentration of the acid in 0.1M-HCl and 0.1M-NaOH respectively from which the value of the thermodynamic constant K_0 may be calculated with the equation³:

$$pK_a = pK_0 + \frac{I^{\frac{1}{2}}}{1 + I^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where I is the ionic strength of the buffer solution.

From Table I, the average value of pK_a comes out as 2.94 ± 0.1 at 30.3° , omitting those in the neighbourhood of the isobestic point (i.e. in the region of wave lengths 425 to 440m μ). This value of pK_a is in satisfactory agreement with the value of 2.91 ± 0.01 (corrected for the ionic strength using equation 2 at 25° , determined potentiometrically⁴). Further, the value of ΔF , as calculated from the above value of thermodynamic ionisation constant according to Van't Hoff's isotherm at 30.3° , comes out to be 4.080×10^3 cal.

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